

Epidemiological, Etiological, Therapeutic, and Evolutionary Profile of Upper Gastrointestinal Bleeding in Adults at the Ibn Rochd University Hospital Center in Casablanca, Morocco

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Abstract

Introduction: Upper gastrointestinal bleeding is a frequent medical and surgical emergency, associated with significant morbidity and mortality. The etiologies of upper gastrointestinal bleeding are dominated by gastroduodenal lesions, particularly peptic ulcers, followed by esophageal varices. Upper gastrointestinal endoscopy remains the first-line examination for etiological investigation. The study has for aim to evaluate the epidemiological, etiological, therapeutic, and prognostic profile of upper gastrointestinal bleeding in adults at the Hepatogastroenterology Department of the Ibn Rochd University Hospital in Casablanca.

Materials and methods: It was a retrospective study conducted on the medical records of adult patients hospitalized for upper gastrointestinal bleeding, from January 1, 2023 to December 31, 2024, who underwent

endoscopic gastrointestinal exploration. Data were entered into an Excel file and analyzed using Jamovi software.

Results: Out of 1,565 admissions for all conditions, 362 cases involved upper gastrointestinal bleeding (23%), of which 20.8% (n = 327) met the inclusion criteria. The mean age was 55 years (range: 16–97 years), with a male-to-female ratio of 1.59. The majority of patients, 77% (n = 252), required hospitalization for more than 72 hours. Concomitant hematemesis and melena was the most frequent reason for hospitalization, observed in 41% (n = 134) of cases. Risk factors for esophageal variceal rupture were the most common, present in 29.4% (n = 96) of patients, including cirrhosis in 23.5% (n = 77) and portal hypertension in 5.8% (n = 19). Toxic habits were reported in 22.9% (n = 75) of patients. A hemorrhagic-risk iatrogenic drug interaction was identified in 16.8% (n = 55), including the use of gastrotoxic drugs in 12.2% (n = 40) and anticoagulants in 4.6% (n = 15).

Esophageal and/or gastric variceal rupture accounted for 38.5% (n = 126) of cases, and gastroduodenal ulcers for 30.3% (n = 99), making them the main etiologies. Regarding management, 61.5% (n = 201) of patients received blood transfusions, among whom 30.6% (n = 100) received more than two units of packed red blood cells. Esophageal variceal ligation was performed in 32.4% (n = 106) of patients. Outcomes were marked by cessation of bleeding in 75.2% (n = 246) of cases. Early rebleeding and in-hospital mortality rates were 9.8% (n = 32) and 5.8% (n = 19), respectively. The causes of death were mainly hepatic encephalopathy in eight cases (2.4%), hemorrhagic shock in four cases (1.2%), respiratory distress in three cases (0.9%), and underlying malignant disease in four cases (1.2%). At discharge, 73.1% (n = 239) of patients had a hemoglobin level between 7 and 10 g/dl and Two patients were transferred to the hematology department. Furthermore, chronic kidney disease, although present in only 1.8% (n=6) of cases, is recognized as an independent risk factor for gastrointestinal bleeding.

Conclusion: Upper gastrointestinal bleeding remains a frequent and severe medical–endoscopic emergency. In Casablanca, the main causes are esophageal variceal rupture and gastroduodenal ulcers, often associated with cirrhosis and the use of gastrotoxic medications, reflecting the significant burden of chronic liver diseases and drug-induced complications in our population. These findings highlight the importance of screening for liver diseases, monitoring high-risk treatments, and improving access to specialized care in order to reduce morbidity and mortality.

Introduction

Upper gastrointestinal bleeding is a common medical–surgical emergency, associated with significant morbidity and mortality despite advances in diagnostic and therapeutic modalities. It is defined as bleeding occurring proximal to the ligament of Treitz and clinically manifests as hematemesis, melena, or more rarely as hematochezia of upper gastrointestinal origin [1]. The etiologies of upper gastrointestinal bleeding are mainly dominated by gastroduodenal lesions, particularly gastroduodenal ulcers, followed by esophageal varices, especially in countries with a high prevalence of chronic liver diseases. Other causes include benign gastric lesions, tumors, and vascular malformations [2]. Upper gastrointestinal endoscopy remains the first-line investigation for etiological diagnosis [3]. The main objective of this study was to describe the epidemiological, etiological, therapeutic, and outcome profiles of upper gastrointestinal bleeding in adult patients hospitalized in the Gastroenterology Department of Ibn Rochd Hospital in Casablanca over a two-year period.

Materials and Methods

This was a retrospective and descriptive study conducted over a two-year period, from January 2023 to December 2024. It included adult patients of both sexes hospitalized in the Gastroenterology Department for upper gastrointestinal bleeding who underwent digestive endoscopic exploration. Patients with upper gastrointestinal bleeding not explored by endoscopy,

hemorrhagic conditions originating from the otorhinolaryngology sphere, and incomplete or unusable medical records were excluded. Data collected from medical records and endoscopy reports were entered into an Excel file and analyzed using Jamovi software.

Results

A total of 1,565 patients were admitted to the department during the study period. Among them, 362 presented with upper gastrointestinal bleeding, representing a hospital frequency of 23%, and 327 met the inclusion criteria.

The mean age of patients was 55 years, with extremes ranging from 16 to 97 years. The most affected age group was 60–70 years, accounting for 27.5% (n = 90) of cases. There was a male predominance (201 men and 126 women), with a male-to-female ratio of 1.59.

Patients from a vulnerable socioeconomic background, particularly those without employment, were the most represented, accounting for 82% (n = 268). A total of 252 patients (77%) were hospitalized for more than 72 hours, compared to 23% (n = 75) who were managed for a shorter duration (≤ 72 hours).

The mean length of hospital stay was 7.39 days, with a range of 1 to 41 days.

The reasons for hospitalization were mainly concomitant hematemesis and melena in 41% (n = 134) of cases, followed by isolated hematemesis in 31.5% (n = 103), as shown in figure 1.

Figure 1: Distribution of Patients According to Reasons for Hospitalization

Among the 327 patients included in the study, 165 patients (50.4%) were being followed for chronic diseases. Seventy-seven patients had chronic liver disease at the stage of cirrhosis (23.5%), of viral or autoimmune origin in 21 cases (7.3%). Diabetes mellitus was present in 13.5% of patients (n = 44). 19 patients (5.8%) had arterial hypertension, of whom seven patients (2.1%) were known to have both diabetes and hypertension. Nineteen patients (5.8%) had portal hypertension.

Thirty patients were followed for various cardiac diseases, among whom 17 were receiving gastrotoxic medications. 10 patients (3.1%) were receiving anticoagulant therapy, and six patients (1.8%) had known chronic kidney disease. Five patients were followed for ischemic stroke and were receiving

gastrotoxic medications. A history of gastroduodenal ulcer disease was found in 12 patients (3.7%), and 11 patients (3.4%) had a previous history of upper gastrointestinal bleeding. 10 patients (3.1%) had a history of neoplasia.

Toxic habits were reported in 22.9% of patients (n = 75). Among them, 50 patients (15%) were smokers without alcohol consumption, 20 patients (6.1%) were both alcohol users and smokers, and 22 patients (6.7%) were alcohol users who did not smoke. Iatrogenic combinations associated with hemorrhagic risk were identified in 55 patients (16.8%), including the use of gastrotoxic drugs in 40 patients (12.2%) and anticoagulants in 15 patients (4.6%). Aspirin use was reported in 21 patients (6.4%), nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) in 18 patients (5.8%), and one patient was receiving dual antiplatelet therapy.

Regarding paraclinical data, emergency laboratory investigations showed that 192 patients (58.7%) had a hemoglobin level below 7 g/dL at admission, with values ranging from 2.2 to 14.9 g/dL. A platelet count below 150,000/mm³ was observed in 122 patients (37.3%), and a decreased prothrombin time (<50%) was found in 29 cases (8.9%). Upper gastrointestinal endoscopy was performed in 327 patients (90.3%), revealing lesions in 93.6% of cases (n = 306).

The most frequent etiology was esophageal and/or gastric varices, accounting for 38.5% of cases (n = 126), followed by gastroduodenal ulcers in 30.3% (n = 99), gastric and/or esophageal tumors in 7.6% (n = 25), acute hemorrhagic gastritis in 7.0% (n = 23), and gastric angiodysplasia in 3.4% (n = 11). Histological examination of biopsy samples confirmed the diagnosis of six cases of gastric adenocarcinoma, four cases of gastric gastrointestinal stromal tumors (GISTs), one case of esophageal carcinoma, and one case of esophageal adenocarcinoma. Among the 99 patients (30.3%) with gastric ulcer as the etiology, seven patients (2.1%) presented with active spurting bleeding classified as Forrest Ia.

Table 1: Distribution of Endoscopic Lesions

Endoscopic Results	Number of patients	Percentage
No lesion	21	6.4
Esophageal and/or gastric varices	126	38.5
Gastro-duodenal ulcers	99	30.3
Gastric/esophageal tumors	25	7,6
Acute hemorrhagic gastritis	23	7.0
Angiodysplasias	11	3,4
Hypertensive gastropathy	8	2.4
Bulbite Bulbitis	7	2.1
Esophagitis	4	1,2
Others	3	0,9
Total	327	100

Figure 2: Representations of the Distribution of Endoscopic Lesions

Pharmacological treatment of bleeding ulcers and acute hemorrhagic gastritis was based on proton pump inhibitors (PPIs) in 59.3% of cases (n = 194). Endoscopic

hemostasis using hemostatic clips was performed in 2.1% of ulcer-related bleeding cases (n = 7), while four cases required surgical hemostasis. 106 patients (32.4%) underwent esophageal variceal ligation (EVL). Twenty patients required biological glue injection for gastric varices.

Furthermore, among the 126 patients hospitalized for esophageal and/or gastric variceal rupture, only 59 patients (18%) received somatostatin prior to the endoscopic procedure, due to the unavailability of this molecule during the study period. Beta-blocker therapy was initiated in 30 newly diagnosed cases among these patients. 11 patients (3.4%) underwent argon plasma coagulation (APC) for gastric angiodysplasia.

A total of 201 patients (61.5%) received blood transfusions, among whom 100 patients (30.6%) received more than two units of packed red blood cells. Outcomes were marked by cessation of bleeding in 246 patients (75.2%). Early rebleeding occurred in 32 patients (9.8%), and five cases (1.5%) developed hemodynamic instability requiring resuscitation with colloids and transfer to the intensive care unit. Two patients were transferred to the hematology department.

19 patients (5.8%) died during hospitalization. The causes of death were mainly hepatic encephalopathy in eight cases (2.4%), hemorrhagic shock in four cases (1.2%), respiratory distress in three cases (0.9%), and underlying malignant disease in four cases (1.2%). At discharge, hemoglobin levels ranged between 7 and 10 g/dL in 239 patients (73.1%).

Table 2: Distribution of Patients According to Their Outcome

Outcome	Number of patients	Percentage
Bleeding cessation	246	75.2
Recurrence	32	9.8
Transfer to other departments	30	9.1
Death	19	5.8
Total	327	100

Discussion

Sociodemographic Characteristics

The results of our study reveal that the majority of upper gastrointestinal bleeding (UGIB) cases occurred in patients aged 60–70 years (27.5%), followed by those aged 49–59 years (20.2%), confirming that the risk of UGIB increases with age. This observation is well documented in the medical literature [2].

Aging is associated with an increase in comorbidities (cirrhosis, peptic ulcers, digestive cancers) and polypharmacy (nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, anticoagulants), which are key risk factors for UGIB. Studies conducted in Marrakech and Dakar have reported similar mean ages, ranging between 60 and 74

years, confirming that UGIB is common beyond the fifth decade of life [4,5].

A clear male predominance was observed, with 61.47% men versus 38.53% women, yielding a male-to-female ratio of 1.59. This finding is consistent with several epidemiological studies highlighting a higher frequency of UGIB among men. In a Moroccan study conducted in Tangier, men accounted for 61.2% of UGIB cases [6]. In Senegal, Khadidiatou reported a sex ratio of 1.82 among patients with UGIB [5]. A large French multicenter study also found male predominance, with a sex ratio of 2.04 [7].

This male predominance may be explained by greater exposure to risk factors such as alcohol consumption,

smoking, non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), and liver cirrhosis of alcoholic or viral origin. The mean length of hospital stay was 7.39 days, with 77% of patients hospitalized for more than 72 hours. In Turkey, the reported average hospital stay is approximately 6.6 days [8]. A U.S. study reported that endoscopy performed within the first day of admission is associated with shorter hospitalization duration [3]. The main reasons for hospitalization were dominated by the association of hematemesis and melena (41%), followed by isolated hematemesis (31.5%) and isolated melena (27.5%). These findings are largely consistent with international and regional literature, while reflecting certain local epidemiological specificities. The predominance of combined hematemesis and melena (41%) in our series is consistent with data reported by Khadidiatou in Senegal, where this presentation was observed in 34.4% of cases, followed by isolated hematemesis (32.3%) and isolated melena (20.8%) [5]. This distribution suggests a patient profile often presenting with severe or high-output UGIB, with a predominance of ulcerative and variceal etiologies in the context of cirrhosis or gastroduodenal ulcer disease.

However, in Western settings, trends may differ. Nahon et al., in a large French multicenter study, showed that isolated melena was the most frequent presenting symptom (73.9%), likely related to better access to healthcare, earlier consultation, and a lower prevalence of variceal bleeding [7]. This discrepancy highlights the importance of local epidemiological context in symptom interpretation.

From a practical standpoint, clinical presentation directly influences endoscopy prioritization, diagnostic strategy, and risk stratification. Accordingly, the European Society of Gastrointestinal Endoscopy (ESGE) recommends incorporating early clinical signs (hematemesis, melena, hemodynamic instability) into prognostic scores such as Rockall or Blatchford to optimize management and reduce morbidity and mortality [9]. The high proportion of hematemesis (isolated or associated with melena) observed in our study underscores the severity of clinical presentations at admission and the urgency of medical intervention, particularly in a setting with a high prevalence of severe hemorrhagic conditions such as esophageal varices.

Medical History

Analysis of our patients' data highlights an epidemiological profile dominated by a population at high hemorrhagic risk due to frequent chronic comorbidities, gastrotoxic treatments, and altered biological parameters.

Burden of Chronic Diseases

More than half of the patients (50.4%) had chronic diseases, particularly chronic liver diseases (23.5%). Cirrhosis represents a major risk factor for hemorrhagic

esophageal varices and accounts for more than 24.6% of UGIB cases among cirrhotic patients, according to Charia Ghada [6]. These findings are consistent with regional Maghreb data reported by El Mekkaoui et al., where viral hepatitis B and C-related cirrhosis remains prevalent, often complicated by portal hypertension [10].

Diabetes mellitus (13.5%), arterial hypertension (5.8%), and cardiovascular history (cardiac diseases, stroke) increase the use of antiplatelet and anticoagulant therapies, explaining the high prevalence of iatrogenic causes of non-cirrhotic UGIB, as highlighted by Catielle et al. [3].

Furthermore, chronic kidney disease, although present in only 1.8% of cases, is recognized as an independent risk factor for gastrointestinal bleeding due to vascular fragility and hemostatic disorders [11].

Toxic Habits and Hemorrhagic Risk

Toxic habits were found in 22.9% of patients (smokers, alcohol users, and combined alcohol-tobacco users) and constitute an important cofactor. Catielle et al. demonstrated that smoking is associated with gastroduodenal mucosal damage and impaired ulcer healing, while alcohol is a direct cause of erosive gastritis and liver cirrhosis [3]. These habits therefore contribute to both variceal and non-variceal causes of UGIB.

Iatrogenic Causes and Gastrotoxic Treatments

A significant proportion of patients (16.8%) had drug combinations associated with hemorrhagic risk, mainly aspirin (6.4%), NSAIDs (5.8%), anticoagulants (4.6%), and dual antiplatelet therapy in one case. These findings are consistent with American series reporting that NSAIDs and antiplatelet agents increase the risk of bleeding ulcers by two- to threefold [3]. NSAIDs impair the gastric mucosal barrier, and even low-dose aspirin significantly increases the risk of hemorrhagic ulcers, particularly in elderly and polymedicated patients.

Digestive History and Recurrence

A history of peptic ulcer disease (3.7%) or previous UGIB (3.4%) highlights the recurrent nature of these events. Secondary prevention with proton pump inhibitors and management of iatrogenic risk factors should be integral to therapeutic strategies, particularly in elderly or polymedicated patients, as emphasized by Lanas et al. [12].

Overall, this profile underscores a population at high risk for UGIB due to the high prevalence of chronic liver disease and gastrotoxic medications. Identification of these risk factors, close follow-up of patients with comorbidities, and improved prevention strategies for iatrogenic causes could help reduce UGIB-related morbidity and mortality.

Etiological Diagnosis

UGIB remains a frequent and potentially severe gastroenterological emergency, with etiologies varying

according to geographic region, healthcare access, and population characteristics. In our series, upper gastrointestinal endoscopy enabled etiological diagnosis in 93.6% of cases, reflecting the effectiveness of systematic endoscopic evaluation within a reasonable timeframe.

Esophageal and/or gastric variceal rupture was the most frequent etiology (38.5%), consistent with data reported in Morocco by Charia Ghada [6]. In contrast, ulcerative causes predominate in Western countries [3]. This high rate reflects the substantial prevalence of chronic liver disease, particularly cirrhosis, in our setting and highlights the impact of local liver disease epidemiology on UGIB lesion profiles.

Gastroduodenal ulcers accounted for 30.3% of UGIB etiologies, comparable to the 29.1% reported by Khadidiatou in Senegal [5], but lower than Western data where peptic ulcers remain the leading cause [7]. In Morocco, Charia Ghada reported a rate of 33%, close to our findings, reflecting an epidemiological transition with increasing variceal etiologies, especially in centers managing large cirrhotic populations [6].

Gastric and esophageal tumors accounted for 7.6% of cases, including adenocarcinomas, gastrointestinal stromal tumors (GISTs), and squamous cell carcinomas. This frequency aligns with other regional and international studies emphasizing the importance of endoscopic biopsy in unexplained bleeding [4, 13].

Angiodysplasia (3.4%) and acute hemorrhagic gastritis (7.0%) remain less frequent but well-documented etiologies, particularly among elderly or polymedicated patients [4, 14].

Management

UGIB remains a frequent gastroenterological emergency with significant morbidity and mortality despite therapeutic advances.

Pharmacological Treatment of Ulcers and Hemorrhagic Gastritis

In our study, 59.3% of patients received proton pump inhibitors (PPIs) for bleeding ulcers or acute hemorrhagic gastritis. This finding is consistent with current guidelines recommending early administration of high-dose intravenous PPIs, particularly in patients with active bleeding or high-risk endoscopic stigmata (Forrest Ia, Ib, or IIa). Continuous PPI infusion during the first 72 hours has been shown to significantly reduce rebleeding, need for surgery, and mortality, as demonstrated by Laine and Jensen [9].

Endoscopic Hemostasis

Endoscopic hemostasis using clips was performed in 2.1% of bleeding ulcer cases, a relatively low rate. According to Gralnek et al., endoscopic therapy should be systematically considered for active or high-risk lesions, often combining epinephrine injection with mechanical (clips) or thermal methods [9].

For gastric angiodysplasia, argon plasma coagulation (APC) was performed in 3.4% of patients. APC is considered the treatment of choice for such lesions [11, 14].

Management of Variceal Bleeding

Among the 327 patients, 106 had esophageal varices and all underwent endoscopic variceal ligation (EVL), in accordance with current recommendations. EVL is the preferred treatment for esophageal variceal bleeding [15].

For the 20 patients with gastric varices, biological glue injection was performed [15, 16]. Only 18% of patients with variceal rupture received vasoactive therapy (somatostatin or its analogues) prior to endoscopy. However, Baveno VII recommendations emphasize immediate initiation of vasoactive drugs upon clinical suspicion of variceal bleeding, ideally within 12 hours [15]. The low rate of vasoactive therapy in our study was due to drug shortages during the study period.

Non-selective beta-blockers were initiated in only 30 patients. Nonetheless, ESGE guidelines and Baveno VII consensus highlight that beta-blockers, combined with EVL, are the cornerstone of secondary prevention of variceal rebleeding [15, 16]. The low initiation rate in our study reflects the fact that most patients were already receiving beta-blockers, and only newly diagnosed cases were considered.

Blood Transfusion

In our series, 201 patients (61.5%) received blood transfusions, with 30.6% receiving more than two units of packed red blood cells. ESGE recommends a transfusion threshold of 7–8 g/dL in hemodynamically stable patients [15]. Similarly, the American College of Gastroenterology supports a restrictive transfusion strategy (threshold of 7 g/dL), with adjustment for patients with cardiovascular disease [17].

Outcomes

Clinical outcomes in our series were comparable to those reported in international and regional studies, underscoring the potential severity of UGIB, particularly in frail patients or those with significant comorbidities.

Bleeding control was achieved in 75.2% of patients, which is encouraging, although slightly lower than rates reported in some series where initial hemostasis approaches 85–90% with modern endoscopic treatments [9, 17]. This may be explained by limited access to advanced endoscopic techniques or delayed management in some cases.

Early rebleeding occurred in 9.8% of cases, consistent with literature data reporting rates between 5% and 15% depending on etiology and initial treatment [7]. This remains concerning, as rebleeding is associated with increased mortality and longer hospital stays [1, 7]. Surgical intervention was required in 3.6% of cases, mainly for hemostatic gastrectomy. While surgery is

now an exceptional option in UGIB management due to advances in endoscopic therapy, it remains necessary in cases of endoscopic failure or inaccessible lesions [1]. The overall mortality rate was 5.8%, comparable to international data where in-hospital mortality ranges from 3% to 10% [7]. The main causes of death were hepatic encephalopathy (2.4%), hemorrhagic shock (1.2%), respiratory distress (0.9%), and malignancies (1.2%). These findings confirm that patients with cirrhosis or digestive cancers represent high-risk groups requiring close monitoring.

Finally, hemoglobin levels at discharge between 7 and 10 g/dL in 73.1% of patients reflect adherence to a restrictive transfusion strategy, now recommended in clinical guidelines, particularly in cirrhotic patients, to reduce complications related to volume overload and rebleeding [15].

Conclusion

Upper gastrointestinal bleeding remains a frequent and severe medical–endoscopic emergency. In Casablanca, the main causes are esophageal variceal rupture and gastroduodenal ulcers, often associated with cirrhosis and the use of gastrotoxic medications, reflecting the substantial burden of chronic liver diseases and drug-induced complications in our population. These findings highlight the importance of screening for liver diseases, careful monitoring of high-risk treatments, and improving access to specialized care to reduce UGIB-related morbidity and mortality.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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